

A Physical Method of Estimating Ferrous and Ferric Iron formed by the Actions of Potassium Dichromate and Potassium Permanganate upon Ferrous Salt.

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In the present investigation the amounts of ferrous and ferric iron have been determined by the use of absorption spectra. A quartz spectrograph was used. An iron arc consuming three amperes was used as the source of light. A Baly's absorption tube with quartz end-plates was used. The width of the slit, the focus, the necessary aperture and the time of exposure were adjusted by taking some trial spectrograms. Standard solutions of ferrous ammonium sulphate, potassium dichromate and potassium permanganate were prepared from Merck's pure chemicals. After taking the absorption spectra of pure solutions, the ferrous salt solution was mixed respectively with potassium dichromate and potassium permanganate in different known proportions. With single solutions or with mixtures of solutions, the length of the absorption column of the Baly's tube was varied and several photographs were taken. The thickness exposed was then expressed in terms of equivalent thickness of $M/10,000$ solution with respect to iron.

The strength of the mixture has been expressed in terms of its iron contents and it has been called 'molar' when it contains 56 g. of iron in 1000 c.c. of the mixture.

Ferrous ammonium sulphate has only total absorption and when it is mixed with either of the oxidizing salts, they lose their characteristic bands and the mixture gives only total absorption. As the composition of the mixture is changed, the absorption border also shifts. The results of the measurements for various mixtures with potassium dichromate and potassium permanganate respectively are graphically represented in Figs. 3 and 4. In these graphs the logarithm of equivalent thickness for $M/10,000$ mixture has been plotted against the corresponding absorption edge.

The absorption borders of mixtures containing different proportions of potassium dichromate and potassium permanganate were

read at $\log t=4$ from the curves shown in Figs. 3 and 4 and the results are graphically shown in Figs. 1 and 2.

The graphs in Figs. 1 and 2 can be used to determine the percentage of ferrous and ferric iron present in a mixture of known iron content, containing the ferrous salt and either of the oxidizing agents in amounts insufficient to oxidize the whole of the ferrous iron.

The absorption spectrum of a mixture of known iron contents (say 0.048M) containing ferrous ammonium sulphate and potassium dichromate is taken at a thickness $t=1/c$ (where c is the molality of the mixture) and it is assumed that the absorption edge lies at 36660 A.U. From graph in Fig. 1, the proportion of ferrous and ferric iron for this absorption edge is 89.45 to 10.55. Since the total quantity of iron in 1000 c.c. is 2.688 g., the quantities of ferrous and ferric iron are 1.4154 g. and 0.2726 g. respectively.

The results thus obtained have been compared with the theoretical ones. The method can be used for estimation of ferrous and ferric iron in a mixture under the conditions stated.

TABLE I.

Potassium Dichromate.

Theoretically calculated.		Physically determined.	
Fe(ous).	Fe(ic).	Fe(ous).	Fe(ic).
98.24	1.76	98.50	1.50
90.02	9.98	89.40	10.60
80.19	19.81	81.20	18.80
64.89	35.61	65.10	34.90
37.47	62.53	36.99	63.01

TABLE II.

Potassium Permanganate.

Theoretically calculated.		Physically determined.	
Fe(ous)	Fe(ic)	Fe(ous)	Fe(ic)
95.72	4.28	96.10	3.90
75.70	24.30	75.90	24.10
64.37	35.63	64.40	35.60
50.40	49.60	50.60	49.40
30.27	69.73	30.67	69.37

FIG. 1.

FIG. 2.

FIG. 3.

FIG. 4.

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